

Supplementary File

To the Manuscript

Who are the plotters behind the pandemic? Comparing Covid-19 conspiracy theories in Google search results across five key target countries of Russia's foreign communication

By

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1. Search terms deployed in the original languages

- USA:
“covid+19”, “covid+19+origin”, "covid+19+truth", "covid+19+conspiracy+theories";
- Germany:
“corona”, “corona+herkunft”, "corona+wahrheit", "corona+verschwörungstheorien";
- Belarus:
“каронавірус”, “каронавірус+паходжанне”,
“каронавірус+біялагічная+зброя”, "каронавірус+праўда",
"каронавірус+тэорыі+змовы";
- Estonia:
“koroonaviiirus”, „koroonaviiiruse+päritolu“, “koroonaviiirus+tõde”,
“koroonaviiirus+vandenõuteooriad“
- Ukraine:
“коронавірус”, “коронавірус+походження”, "коронавірус+правда",
"коронавірус+теорії+змови";
- Russia:
“коронавирус”, “коронавирус+происхождение”, "коронавирус+правда",
"коронавирус+теории+заговора".

2. Code

The Python code used to collect data for this study is openly available in the following GitHub repository:

<https://github.com/polcomm-passau/searching-conspiracy-theories>

3. Data sets

The following three data sets are provided as supplementary files to the manuscript:

- Full data set (N=4.400)

CT_DS_Full.sav

- Data set containing only results that feature undebunked conspiratorial accounts (N=303)

CT_DS_Only_CTs.sav

- Data set comprising means of conspiratorial accounts by country by search term (N=20)

CT_DS_Means_Confirmatory_Accounts_Country.sav

4. Intercoder reliability tests

In this project, we followed what Rössler (2013) has referred to a “project language proceeding” (p. 463), i.e. we did all the coder training and tests in the project language, i.e. in English.

The initial version of the codebook was created by the authors of the study between April 2020 and September 2020. During this time period, the codebook was revised repeatedly, after numerous preliminary coding sessions and discussions in the research team (primarily with reference to exploratory analysis of small numbers of Russian, German, and English language web pages).

In the next step, intercoder reliability tests were conducted between two individuals whom we chose as *primary coders*. These reliability tests were conducted on a random sample of 175 English language news items retrieved in November 2020. The primary coders were fluent in English, Russian, and German. The test values achieved were as follows:

Variable	Percent agreement	Krippendorff's alpha
V8: Type of Source	85.7%	.842
V9: Geographical Origin of Source	87.9%	.832
V10: Russia's Influence on Source	95.9%	.915
V11: Accessibility of Website	100%	1
V12: Actual Item Language	99.0%	.663
V13: Date of Publication	100%	1
V14: Title of the Item	100%	1
V15: Presence of Pay Wall	97.0%	.388
V16: Presence of Conspiracy Theories	91.8%	.862
V17: Specific Conspiracy Plots		
V17a: Biological Weapon	92.6%	.854
V17b: 5G Towers	96.3%	.784
V17c: Control Through Vaccine	96.3%	.839
V17d: Different Origin	81.5%	.618
V17e: Distortion of Information	74.1%	.442
V18: Geographical Origin of Plotter	81.5%	.723
V19: Geographical Origin of Victim	63%	.447

In order to add data for smaller countries (whose languages the primary coders did not master), we recruited two assistant coders who were fluent in Ukrainian, Belarusian, and English (assistant coder 1) and Estonian and English (assistant coder 2). Each of the two assistant coders had to pass several test rounds, in which they were assigned 50 pre-coded English language items. After each test round, one of the two primary coders checked the results, and went through the mistakes in the English language pre-coded dataset together with the assistant coder. As a result, assistant coders acquired an in-depth understanding of how the variables had to be coded.

The actual coding for the smaller countries was then conducted in a meeting of the primary coder and the assistant coder. For this meeting, the assistant coder prepared a pre-coded data sheet, in which cases that were most likely uncontroversial (for instance, web pages that did not mention conspiracy theories at all) were highlighted. In the joint coding session, the primary and the assistant coder then completed and double-checked the pre-coded data sheet, going through the data sheet item by item. During the joint session, the primary coder frequently used the help of an automated translation tool.